

A Novel Approach for Fuzzy Online Portfolio Selection Model Using Dual Beta and Trading Volume

M. Abdi¹, S. B. Ebrahimi² and A. A. Najafi³

¹ Department of Industrial Engineering, K.N. Toosi University of Technology, No. 17, Pardis Avenue, Mollasadra Street, Vanak Square, Tehran, Iran;
Email : matinabdi@email.kntu.ac.ir

² Department of Industrial Engineering, K.N. Toosi University of Technology, No. 17, Pardis Avenue, Mollasadra Street, Vanak Square, Tehran, Iran;
Email : b_ebrahimi@kntu.ac.ir

³ Department of Industrial Engineering, K.N. Toosi University of Technology, No. 17, Pardis Avenue, Mollasadra Street, Vanak Square, Tehran, Iran;
Email : aanajafi@kntu.ac.ir

ABSTRACT

The online portfolio selection has gained significant interest in recent years. It involves allocating capital among assets and updating the portfolio to maximize long-term return. This research presents an online portfolio selection algorithm incorporating fuzzy returns, dual-beta risk measure, and trading volume. The algorithm employs dual-beta to achieve maximum utility by exploiting positive market movements while avoiding negative ones. To make the model more realistic, each day's return is represented as a fuzzy number, which avoids the simplifying assumption of trading at the stock's closing price. Another key feature of this study is using trading volume to identify similar time windows. The algorithm presented in this study follows the pattern-matching principle. Fuzzy clustering is used in the sample selection step to cluster fuzzy returns and trading volumes. This helps identify time windows similar to the recent one, using Manhattan and Canberra distance criteria. In the portfolio optimization step, an optimal logarithmic objective function with the dual-beta risk measure incorporating transaction costs is employed. The algorithm underwent evaluation by testing it on five datasets of different time intervals and characteristics. The evaluation results demonstrate a substantial enhancement in returns and risk-adjusted returns compared to prior algorithms in the literature.

Keywords: Pattern-matching, Fuzzy return, C-Means clustering, Dual-beta, Trading volume.

Regression, data structure, prediction, simulation.

Mathematics Subject Classification: 91G10, 91B60, 91B86, 62P05

Computing Classification System: I.4

1. INTRODUCTION

Portfolio selection models have attracted considerable attention from investors in recent years. Markowitz (1952) introduced his portfolio selection theory by balancing expected returns (mean) with risk (variance). As trading volumes and speed of transactions in financial markets have increased, there has been a growing inclination towards using algorithmic trading techniques for portfolio selection.

Online portfolio selection models have gained significant attention in recent years. Most online portfolio selection models are derived from Kelly's capital growth theory (1956). The objective of this theory is to optimize investment returns by maximizing the expected logarithm, making it ideal for multi-period decision-making. In contrast, Markowitz's theory is not as suitable for this purpose. Kelly-based methods inherently emphasize long-term portfolio returns, which may cause higher investment risk.

In the literature on online portfolio selection, three basic approaches are noted: follow the winner, follow the loser, and pattern-matching. Studies in this area show that among these approaches, the pattern-matching approach which designs portfolios based on similar historical patterns has empirically shown higher returns (Li & Hoi, 2014). The implementation of the model using pattern-matching algorithms involves two distinct steps: sample selection and portfolio optimization. In the process of sample selection, recent data is compared with historical data, and samples that bear resemblance to the recent data are selected. The subsequent stage involves selecting the optimal portfolio by considering the similarity of each data in the chosen samples.

1.1. Research background

The current research introduces an algorithm for online portfolio selection that is based on the principle of pattern-matching. It incorporates fuzzy returns, a dual-beta risk measure, and takes trading volume into consideration. In this section, relevant studies conducted in this field are reviewed. The literature on online portfolio selection places significant emphasis on the principle of pattern-matching. This method utilizes historical data to determine the portfolio allocation for the forthcoming period by identifying historical patterns that closely resemble the recent one. These algorithms have consistently demonstrated superior capital growth when compared to alternative online portfolio selection methods. Generally, pattern-matching algorithms comprise two key steps: sample selection and portfolio optimization. The step of sample selection aims to identify time windows that bear resemblance to the recent one. Based on the selected similar samples, the optimal portfolio is constructed through the portfolio optimization step.

The B^K strategy was implemented, integrating the kernel method in the initial step and logarithmic optimization in the subsequent step (Györfi et al., 2006). To simplify the calculations in the B^K algorithm, the B^S strategy was introduced using a semi-logarithmic optimization method in the second step (Györfi et al., 2007). To balance return and risk, the B^M strategy was developed by incorporating Markowitz's approach. In the initial step of this strategy, the kernel method is combined with Markowitz's method in the subsequent step (Ottucsák & Vajda, 2007). Subsequently, to include transaction costs in portfolio optimization, the B^{GV} strategy was introduced (Györfi & Vajda, 2008). The initial step of the B^{NN} strategy involves the utilization of the nearest neighbor method, while the second step employs logarithmic optimization (Györfi et al., 2008). The CORN strategy, which combines correlation and logarithmic optimization, has outperformed previous algorithms in empirical studies (Li et al., 2011). The risk-averse pattern-matching algorithm RACORN was developed using the CORN strategy (Wang et al., 2018). Later, the DRICORN algorithm, which incorporates dynamic risk, was proposed based on the same strategy (Sooklal et al., 2020). A new online portfolio selection model was introduced that incorporates

transaction costs into portfolio optimization. The model uses four clustering algorithms (K-Means, K-Medoids, spectral clustering, and hierarchical clustering) for sample selection (Khedmati & Azin, 2020). A pattern-matching-based online portfolio selection algorithm was enhanced to include the mean-variance strategy. This algorithm not only considers return and risk but also incorporates environmental, social, and governance factors (Fereydooni et al., 2024). The development of an online portfolio selection algorithm, which integrates the principles of pattern-matching and fuzzy clustering, was carried out, with the incorporation of the beta risk measure (Abdi et al., 2024). A recent development in online portfolio selection involves the introduction of an algorithm that incorporates the pattern-matching principle. This algorithm, known as PMDI (Pattern-Matching Dual Information), utilizes dual information on direction and distance to locate similar data (He, 2024). The Online Portfolio Selection with Dynamic Coreset Construction (PSCS) algorithm was proposed. PSCS uses a unique clustering process to group assets and creates a core set for solving optimization problems (Peng et al., 2024). Online portfolio selection algorithms assume stocks are traded at the closing price, which deviates from reality and excludes a significant portion of the data from modeling. To make the model more realistic and account for the highest and lowest daily prices of each stock, an online portfolio selection algorithm was developed. This algorithm uses triangular fuzzy returns and fuzzy clustering, and it is based on the pattern-matching principle (Abdi et al., 2023). A study was conducted to develop an online portfolio selection model by combining an adaptive Kalman filter with a fuzzy logic approach for enhanced prediction and dynamic asset allocation (Sirirut & Thongtha, 2022).

Zadeh (1965) first introduced the concepts of fuzzy sets through the membership function, which laid the foundation for fuzzy decision-making theory (Bellman & Zadeh, 1970). A portfolio selection model using a three-objective function including return, risk, and liquidity, and also using the semi-absolute standard deviation as a risk measure while considering transaction costs, was modeled through fuzzy decision-making theory (Parra et al., 2001). A portfolio selection model was proposed according to mean, variance, skewness, and kurtosis using fuzzy returns and employing fuzzy credibility theory for model resolution (Kamdem et al., 2012). A comprehensive portfolio selection model was suggested based on fuzzy credibility theory, where return and risk are calculated via expected value and variance, with liquidity considered as a constraint in the model (Gupta, 2013). Using triangular fuzzy numbers and the principles of fuzzy credibility theory, a portfolio selection model was developed, focusing on mean, variance, and skewness (Qin, 2017). A fuzzy portfolio selection model using semi-variance, skewness, semi-kurtosis, and semi-entropy within the framework of fuzzy credibility theory was proposed (Rahimi & Kumar, 2019). Another fuzzy portfolio selection model was developed using mean, variance, and skewness under the fuzzy credibility theory (Pahade & Jha, 2021). A multi-period portfolio selection model was introduced, focusing on maximizing returns and minimizing risk, with returns computed using fuzzy numbers based on pessimistic, optimistic, and realistic scenarios (Deng & Chen, 2021). A model for portfolio selection using fuzzy returns was proposed to maximize returns and minimize value at risk (MirAboalhassani et al., 2022). A portfolio selection model based on investor preferences was introduced, employing LR fuzzy numbers for expected returns and liquidity, with a genetic algorithm used for solving the model (Jalota et al., 2023). The fuzzy portfolio selection model (FPSMSC) has been

introduced, offering a balanced efficient frontier in portfolio selection and considering fuzzy expertise knowledge to anticipate stock price movements. (Jo et al., 2024)

1.2. Research contributions

Most online portfolio selection algorithms assume trading with the closing price of the stock, which deviates from reality. In fact, every stock is traded between the lowest, and the highest price of the day and there is no certainty in trading the stock with the closing price. Online portfolio selection models can be improved by incorporating fuzzy return, which helps address uncertainty in stock trading prices and make the models more realistic. The uncertainty in financial markets has led to the widespread use of fuzzy concepts in portfolio selection models, as they align with market needs. Another noteworthy point in the algorithms presented in online portfolio selection is the focus on obtaining the maximum return, regardless of the risk of the selected portfolio. In fact, every investor considers the two essential criteria of return and risk simultaneously to choose an investment portfolio. Hence, portfolio selection models strive to maximize returns and minimize risk in a manner that yields the most favorable outcomes according to these criteria. To accomplish this goal, the incorporation of risk measures in modeling is essential. One of the risk measures to use in online portfolio selection models is the beta risk measure. The risk measure can be used to maximize utility by leveraging the dual-beta risk measure. This strategy capitalizes on positive market fluctuations while mitigating negative ones. A noteworthy characteristic of models based on the pattern-matching principle is their exclusive reliance on stock returns during the sample selection phase. However, a significant factor in identifying similar historical patterns is the trading volume of each stock on each day. The price increase in a stock with high trading volume behaves differently from the same price increase with low trading volume. The sample selection step aims to maximize similarity between the decision day and past days. Including trading volume will significantly affect the process of finding similar days.

To address the issues highlighted, a novel online portfolio selection algorithm is introduced in this study. The algorithm operates on the principle of pattern-matching and integrates fuzzy returns. The sample selection step in this algorithm involves two clustering steps. First, the fuzzy returns are clustered, and then the trading volume is clustered using the fuzzy clustering method to extract similar samples. The portfolio is optimized in the portfolio optimization step by maximizing the logarithm of return, considering transaction cost, and maximizing or minimizing the dual-beta of the portfolio based on market condition prediction.

In section 2, the theoretical foundations of the research, including fuzzy returns, trading volume, fuzzy clustering of fuzzy data, and dual-beta risk measure, are discussed. In section 3, the formulation of the problem and the explanation of the proposed algorithm will be discussed. In section 4, the results of implementing the proposed algorithm on real data and comparing it with other algorithms presented in the literature and benchmark algorithms will be presented. Furthermore, in section 5, conclusions and suggestions for future studies will be presented.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF RESEARCH

This section delves into the theoretical underpinnings of the research, encompassing four fundamental concepts employed in the algorithm presented. These four concepts include fuzzy returns, trading volume, fuzzy clustering of fuzzy data, and dual-beta risk measure, each of which has been investigated separately.

2.1. Fuzzy returns

As mentioned, the assumption of trading at the closing price is a simplifying assumption used in many online portfolio selection algorithms. Given that a stock can be traded within a range between its daily maximum and minimum prices, considering trading only at the closing price is unrealistic. To make the model more realistic and include a broader range of data, Abdi et al. (2023) suggested representing daily stock returns as a triangular fuzzy number. This involves incorporating the lowest and highest trading prices of each stock.

$$\xi(\text{Price Ratio}_t) = \left(\frac{\text{Low Price}_t}{\text{Close Price}_{t-1}}, \frac{\text{Close Price}_t}{\text{Close Price}_{t-1}}, \frac{\text{High Price}_t}{\text{Close Price}_{t-1}} \right)$$

By incorporating fuzzy returns and using both the maximum and minimum prices of a stock in the calculations, the model becomes more realistic. This allows for a simultaneous consideration of a comprehensive set of data for finding similar time windows. As a result, it is expected that selecting similar data with higher accuracy will lead to better results from the algorithm.

2.2. Trading volume

One factor influencing the exchange of each stock and its price determination is the trading volume on any day. For instance, a 2% price increase in a stock with high trading volume behaves differently from a 2% price increase in a stock with low trading volume. The sample selection step aims to maximize similarity between the decision day and previous days. Identifying similar days based on trading volume is crucial in this process. The proposed algorithm includes two clustering stages to find similar data. In the first stage, clustering is performed using the return matrix, and in the second stage, clustering is based on trading volume. For this purpose, a matrix comprising the trading volume of each stock on each day is constructed. These numbers are then normalized because of the significant differences in trading volumes among stocks. A second clustering is performed on the data from the first stage, based on trading volume, if the number of similar days surpasses a certain threshold. Finally, the similar data got from the second clustering stage form the basis for the portfolio optimization step.

2.3. Fuzzy clustering of fuzzy data

Clustering techniques are used to identify natural groupings within data, where data points that are similar in certain aspects are placed in the same cluster. The aim is to organize data into groups where members of each group are similar in a particular feature while having the least similarity with members of other clusters. The similarity criterion in clustering is the distance, and the method of calculating this

distance is important. By determining the distance between two data points, their proximity can be assessed, and they can be grouped within the same cluster.

The Fuzzy C-Means clustering technique is a development of the K-Means method, and its logic closely resembles that of K-Means. In Fuzzy C-Means clustering, clusters are defined by setting a central point and grouping data points based on their proximity to the central point, similar to K-Means. The utilization of fuzzy clustering permits the allocation of data points to multiple clusters, accompanied by a precise membership degree for each cluster. In traditional fuzzy clustering methods, the number of clusters is fixed and is entered as an input at the beginning of the algorithm.

In the literature, various methods are proposed for calculating the distance between fuzzy data points. One such method, known as the weighting system approach, involves calculating the distance between the centers and spreads of two fuzzy numbers. This approach seeks to estimate the distance between two fuzzy numbers by assigning appropriate weights to the distances between their centers and the spreads of the fuzzy numbers.

The Manhattan and Canberra distance criteria are used in this research. These criteria employ the weighting system approach to compute the distance between each data point and the cluster centers for triangular fuzzy numbers.

$$d(\tilde{x}_i, \tilde{v}_j) = w_c [d(c_i, c_j)] + w_s [d(l_i, l_j) + d(r_i, r_j)]$$

Where w_c is the weight of the fuzzy number's center and w_s is the weight of its spreads. Typically, the center weight is greater because the center's membership degree is higher. Therefore, it is generally true that $w_c \geq w_s \geq 0$ and $w_c + w_s = 1$, with $0.5 \leq w_c \leq 1$.

2.4. Fuzzy clustering of fuzzy data

One of the key risk measures used to assess the sensitivity of a stock or portfolio to market changes is the beta coefficient. The beta coefficient measures systematic risk and shows how much the return of an asset changes in response to changes in the market return. The beta coefficient of a stock is calculated using its historical returns, as shown in the following:

$$\beta_i = \frac{cov(R_i, R_m)}{var(R_m)}$$

Where R_i and R_m indicate the daily return of stock i and the daily return of the market index, respectively. The beta coefficient possesses a similar interpretation to the regression coefficient within a linear regression model. It indicates the size and orientation of alterations in the return of a stock or portfolio relative to market adjustments. Additionally, the beta coefficient of a portfolio containing stocks can be derived by employing the following formula:

$$\beta_p = \sum_{i=1}^m w_i \cdot \beta_i$$

Where w_i denotes the weight of stock i in the portfolio.

Dual-beta was introduced to enhance the traditional beta risk measure, which allows for differentiation between the risks associated with positive and negative market movements. In the traditional beta calculation, no distinction is made between the coefficients of positive and negative market changes. This can cause an overestimation of upside risk or an underestimation of downside risk. Considering that markets behave differently during uptrends and downtrends, dual-beta was developed to distinguish the sensitivity of a stock to market changes in both bullish and bearish conditions. To calculate dual-beta, the market index's up and down days are separated, and the downside and upside betas are computed for each stock in bullish and bearish markets, respectively, as follows:

$$\text{Upside beta: } \beta_i^+ = \frac{\text{cov}(R_i, R_m^+)}{\text{var}(R_m^+)}$$

$$\text{Downside beta: } \beta_i^- = \frac{\text{cov}(R_i, R_m^-)}{\text{var}(R_m^-)}$$

The algorithm proposed in this study aims to exploit positive risk and avoid negative risk. In pursuit of this goal, a penalty is enforced on portfolios or stocks displaying high beta values to alleviate the risk of portfolio depreciation when a bearish market is predicted. Conversely, a reward is assigned to portfolios or stocks with high beta values to maximize the returns from positive market movements when a bullish market is expected. Hence, dual-beta is used with the goal of maximizing positive beta in an expected bull market and minimizing negative beta in an expected bear market. Therefore, the objective function of the online portfolio selection model integrates the beta risk measure, with a coefficient as indicated in the following equation:

$$Z = E\{\log(b \odot (1 - TC)) \cdot y \mid y_i, i \in C(x_1^t)\} \pm \lambda \beta_i^\pm$$

In the above equation, λ is a hyperparameter representing the beta coefficient. Term $\lambda \beta_p^+$ is included in the model when a bullish market is predicted, and term $\lambda \beta_p^-$ is subtracted from the model in the event of a bearish market. The objective of this approach is to optimize profits from market fluctuations.

It is crucial to make a market condition prediction for the forthcoming decision period. This entails the classification of data in order to ascertain whether the market will experience an upward or downward trend. The DRICORN algorithm utilizes seven methods for both data classification and market condition forecasting. These methods are categorized into three major groups: pure price variation, comparison between current and lagged moving averages on cumulative returns, and moving linear regression analysis to price relative vectors. The findings of the conducted studies indicate that the moving linear regression method exhibits a greater level of correspondence with reality compared to other methods (Sooklal et al., 2020).

Based on these results, in this study, simple and weighted linear regression analysis on the market index data is used to predict the market condition.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section will first explain the problem formulation, including the definition of the variables and parameters used in the model. Next, the proposed algorithm in this study will be presented.

Table 1 displays the variables and formulation utilized in the fuzzy online portfolio selection algorithm developed within this study.

Table 1: The variables and formulation of the proposed algorithm

	m	The number of portfolio stocks
	n	Investment period
	$P_t^L = (p_{t,1}^L, p_{t,2}^L, \dots, p_{t,j}^L, \dots, p_{t,m}^L)$	The vector of low price of stocks
	$P_t^M = (p_{t,1}^M, p_{t,2}^M, \dots, p_{t,j}^M, \dots, p_{t,m}^M)$	The vector of closing price of stocks
	$P_t^H = (p_{t,1}^H, p_{t,2}^H, \dots, p_{t,j}^H, \dots, p_{t,m}^H)$	The vector of high price of stocks
	$P = (P_t^L, P_t^M, P_t^H)$	The three-dimensional matrix of low, high, and closing price of stocks
	$x_t^L; \quad x_{t,i}^L = \frac{p_{t,i}^L}{p_{t-1,i}^M}$	The low price-relative vector of stocks
	$x_t^M; \quad x_{t,i}^M = \frac{p_{t,i}^M}{p_{t-1,i}^M}$	The closing price-relative vector of stocks
	$x_t^H; \quad x_{t,i}^H = \frac{p_{t,i}^H}{p_{t-1,i}^M}$	The high price-relative vector of stocks
	$X = (x_t^L, x_t^M, x_t^H)$	The three-dimensional matrix of low, high, and closing price-relative of stocks, the matrix including fuzzy returns
$Y_t;$	$y_{t,i} = \frac{x_{t,i}^L + 2 * x_{t,i}^M + x_{t,i}^H}{4}$	The expected return vector of fuzzy returns using the fuzzy credibility theory
	V	The two-dimensional matrix of trading volume of stocks
	$b_t = (b_{t,1}, \dots, b_{t,m})$	The investment ratios of stocks at the beginning of each period
	$S_t = b_t^T y_t = \sum_{i=1}^m b_{t,i} y_{t,i}$	Gained return by the end of each period

The algorithm proposed an online portfolio selection algorithm. It constructs a portfolio of stocks and decides at the beginning of each period regarding the weight of each stock in the portfolio and then executes buy and sell transactions. The algorithm primarily focuses on considering the total return at the end of the final investment period as the main output in the long run. This algorithm is like all algorithms that follow the pattern-matching principle and includes two key steps: sample selection and portfolio optimization.

3.1. Sample selection step in the proposed algorithm

In the sample selection step, the algorithm searches the historical data to find data that shows similar behavior to the most recent time window (TW). The model's input is the price data matrix, from which the price relative matrix is extracted. Subsequent to this, the training and test data are partitioned in accordance with the train ratio. The training matrix is subsequently subdivided into sub-matrices of size TW, based on the length of the time window. These sub-matrices are then clustered to identify those that belong to the same cluster as the most recent submatrix. To perform clustering, the sub-matrices are first unwrapped into vectors. The resulting vectors from the sub-matrices undergo clustering through the C-Means algorithm. To calculate the distance between two fuzzy numbers, the Manhattan and Canberra distances are used, following the described weighting system in Section 2-3. The objective

function of the clustering model is minimized to select the optimal number of clusters. Sub-matrices that resemble the most recent submatrix are classified as similar.

Considering trading volume during the sample selection step, an additional clustering phase is performed using trading volume data. In this phase, the normalized trading volume matrix for each stock on each day is considered as the model's input. The normalization of trading volumes is performed because of the significant differences in trading volumes among different stocks. If the number of similar sub-matrices from the previous stage exceeds a specified threshold, a second clustering step is conducted. This second step focuses on the data obtained from the first clustering step and incorporates trading volume. This includes extracting the sub-matrices corresponding to similar sub-matrices from the first clustering step from the trading volume matrix and then applying fuzzy clustering to these sub-matrices. Sub-matrices clustered with the most recent submatrix are chosen as similar data. If the number of sub-matrices from the first clustering step is greater than a specified threshold, each similar submatrix from the second clustering step is considered a similar day and recorded. Otherwise, the similar sub-matrices from the first step are considered as similar sub-matrices, and the day following them is recorded as a similar day. Finally, the correlation between the membership vectors of the similar sub-matrices and the most recent submatrix is calculated. Each submatrix is assigned a weight based on the correlation of its membership vector with the membership vector of the most recent submatrix, following normalization.

3.2. Portfolio optimization step of the proposed algorithm

In the portfolio optimization step, the optimal portfolio for the decision day is derived by analyzing the price-relative matrix of similar days and their associated weights, which are determined and identified in the previous step. A uniform portfolio is chosen for the first day of the testing period. In case no similar sample is identified, the portfolio remains unchanged. Otherwise, the optimal portfolio is determined by solving the following optimization model.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \max \quad & Z = E\{\log(b \odot (1 - TC)) \cdot y \mid y_i, i \in C(x_1^t)\} \pm \lambda \beta_p^\pm \\
 & = \log\left((b \odot (1 - TC)) \cdot C\right) \cdot W \pm \lambda \beta_p^\pm \\
 & = \sum_{i \in C(x_1^t)} w_i \log(b \odot (1 - TC)) \cdot c_i \pm \lambda \sum_{i=1}^m w_i \beta_i^\pm \\
 \text{s. t.} \quad & \sum b_i = 1 \\
 & l \leq b_i \leq u \quad \forall i
 \end{aligned}$$

In portfolio optimization, the fuzzy credibility theory is used to solve the model by considering fuzzy returns.

In the objective function of the model, which is of the logarithmic type, the matrix C and vector W obtained from the first step represent the matrix of similar days and the vector of weights for similar days, respectively. The vector TC represents the transaction cost percentages, calculated as follows:

$$TC = |B_{adj}(t - 1) - b| \odot \tau$$

$$\tau = \begin{cases} TCBuy & B_{adj}(t-1) - b < 0 \\ TCSell & B_{adj}(t-1) - b > 0 \\ 0 & B_{adj}(t-1) - b = 0 \end{cases}$$

The dual-beta β_p^\pm and the hyperparameter λ are added to the model. Specifically, if the market is forecasted to be bullish, the term $\lambda\beta_p^+$ is added to the model to maximize the upside beta. Conversely, if the market is forecasted to be bearish, the term $\lambda\beta_p^-$ is subtracted from the model to minimize the downside beta, thus maximizing returns from market changes. In order to determine the market's bullish or bearish nature, a straightforward and weighted linear regression is conducted on the market index data, placing greater emphasis on recent data. When the regression calculation yields a positive slope, the model will include the term $\lambda\beta_p^+$ with a positive sign. On the other hand, when the slope is negative, the model will include the term $\lambda\beta_p^-$ with a negative sign. Through the process of optimizing the model mentioned earlier, we arrive at the value b^* , which denotes the potential optimal portfolio for the forthcoming day.

When each day starts, each stock in the portfolio is allocated a specific weight. As prices fluctuate, the weights of the stocks in the portfolio will likewise experience alterations throughout the day. Ultimately, a new weight is assigned by taking into account the revised prices. The weight assigned to the portfolio at the end of the day is commonly known as the adjusted portfolio weight. Indeed, when no trades are made, the weights of the stocks solely fluctuate due to changes in prices. The calculation for the adjusted portfolio weight is determined as follows:

$$B_{adj}(t) = \frac{B^*(t) \odot x^M(t)}{B^*(t) x^M(t)}$$

It is crucial to emphasize that the algorithm does not have a predetermined time window size. On the contrary, the algorithm establishes the most suitable time window for each day by taking into account the outcomes of model optimization in previous periods.

Once the following day arrives and the market price information for that day is revealed, the returns resulting from the decisions made on that day are assessed. The current period is subsequently transferred to the training matrix, and this sequential process persists until the conclusion of the investment period.

Based on the explained algorithm, four distinct algorithms have been developed for this research, which are shown in Table 2. The overall process of the proposed algorithm is summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The process of the proposed algorithm

Figure 1. (Continued) The process of the proposed algorithm

Figure 1. (Continued) The process of the proposed algorithm

Table 2: Steps of the proposed algorithms.

Algorithm	Sample selection step	Portfolio optimization step
FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw)	Two-stage clustering with fuzzy clustering at each stage using the Canberra distance criterion	Maximizing the logarithm of return by considering dual-beta and forecasting the market situation using simple linear regression
FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw)	Two-stage clustering with fuzzy clustering at each stage using the Manhattan distance criterion	Maximizing the logarithm of return by considering dual-beta and forecasting the market situation using simple linear regression
FCM(can)-DRLOG(ew)	Two-stage clustering with fuzzy clustering at each stage using the Canberra distance criterion	Maximizing the logarithm of return by considering dual-beta and forecasting the market situation using weighted linear regression
FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew)	Two-stage clustering with fuzzy clustering at each stage using the Manhattan distance criterion	Maximizing the logarithm of return by considering dual-beta and forecasting the market situation using weighted linear regression

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

The implementation of the proposed algorithm on actual data and its performance comparison with previous algorithms have been conducted in this section. Moreover, this section provides an explanation of the assumed parameters and showcases the application of the proposed algorithm on datasets exhibiting unique characteristics, thereby enhancing the empirical evidence.

4.1. Parameters and datasets description

To compare the results obtained from the proposed algorithm with previous algorithms, the implementation was carried out using five datasets employed by Khedmati & Azin (2020) and also by Abdi et al. (2023). This allows for the comparison of results using standard datasets. The mentioned datasets are selected from the U.S. stock market and vary in terms of different markets, periods, and the number of stocks. Using these datasets not only enables comparison with previous research but also allows for the examination of various parameters. The characteristics of each dataset are as follows:

- Dataset 1 is from the NASDAQ market and includes 15 stocks over the period from January 2016 to December 2017. This timeframe experienced a bullish market, and the testing covers the last 126 days of this period.
- Dataset 2 comprises 15 stocks from the NYSE, which were selected during a bullish market condition from January 2016 to December 2017. The algorithm is evaluated over 126 days.
- Dataset 3 includes 10 stocks from the NASDAQ-100, which covers January 2013 to December 2015. The market was bullish during this period, and testing was conducted over 188 days.
- Dataset 4 comprises 30 stocks from the Dow Jones market, which were selected during a bullish condition from January 2011 to December 2013. The algorithm is evaluated over 188 days.

- Dataset 5 contains 20 stocks from the S&P 500 for the period from January 2000 to December 2001, which were selected during a bearish condition. This dataset is assessed over 125 days.

To better compare the results with other studies, the following parameters from previous research were used:

- Train Ratio: Set at 75%, meaning that three-fourths of the data is used for training the algorithm and one-fourth for testing it.
- Fuzzification Degree: Set to 2 in the fuzzy clustering objective function.
- Weighting System: For calculating the distance between two fuzzy numbers, $w_s = 0.3$ and $w_c = 0.7$ were used.
- Dual-Beta Calculation: The dual-beta values for the portfolio were calculated using the market indices for each dataset. The composite NASDAQ index was used for Dataset 1, the NYSE composite index for Dataset 2, the NASDAQ-100 index for Dataset 3, the Dow Jones index for Dataset 4, and the S&P 500 index for Dataset 5.
- Regression Period: A 60-day period was used for calculating the linear regression on the market index data for each dataset.
- Weighted Linear Regression: Exponential weighting was applied to give more weight to recent data compared to older data.
- Beta Coefficient λ : Set to 0.001 in the model.
- Transaction Costs: The buy transaction cost was set to zero, while the sell transaction cost was set to the maximum value of 0.005.
- Sharpe Ratio Calculation: The risk-free rate used for calculating the annual Sharpe ratio was considered as the treasury bond rate, assumed to be 2.5%.

4.2. Results from the implementation of the algorithms on datasets

This section details the evaluation measurements for the implementation of the proposed algorithms which is presented in the form of four separate algorithms for each of the five datasets.

Table 3: The outcomes achieved by implementing the proposed algorithms on Dataset 1.

Evaluation Measurements	Results			
	FCM(can)- DRLOG(uw)	FCM(man)- DRLOG(uw)	FCM(can)- DRLOG(ew)	FCM(man)- DRLOG(ew)
Cumulative Return	1.6308	1.7100	1.5800	1.6546
Annualized Return	165.94%	192.42%	149.65%	173.76%
Annualized Standard Deviation of Returns	0.3241	0.3556	0.3569	0.3571
Annualized Sharpe Ratio	5.0424	5.3405	4.1234	4.7955
Maximum Drawdown	0.1543	0.1683	0.1959	0.1959
Calmar Ratio	10.7552	11.4331	7.6391	8.8697

Dataset 1- The evaluation measurements for the proposed algorithms applied on Dataset 1 are displayed in Table 3. The FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw) algorithm got the highest cumulative and annualized return of 1.7100 and 192.42%, respectively, in terms of returns. The FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw) algorithm exhibited the lowest risk, with an annual standard deviation of 0.3241 and a maximum drawdown of 0.1543. The FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw) algorithm was the best-performing algorithm in terms of risk-adjusted returns and achieved an annualized Sharpe ratio of 5.3405 and a Calmar ratio of 11.4331. Figure 2 displays the accumulated daily returns obtained by executing the algorithms on Dataset 1.

Figure 2. The daily cumulative return of the proposed algorithms implemented on Dataset 1

Dataset 2- The results obtained from implementing the proposed algorithms on Dataset 2 are presented in Table 4. The FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew) algorithm showed the highest cumulative return and annual percentage yield of 1.8738 and 251.12%, respectively. This algorithm also recorded the highest Sharpe ratio of 4.3454. FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw) has the lowest annual standard deviation of 0.4063 and the smallest maximum drawdown of 0.1173, which shows that this algorithm carries the least risk among the presented algorithms. Also, this algorithm had the highest Calmar ratio of 13.3290. Daily cumulative returns obtained from implementing the algorithms on Dataset 2 are shown in Figure 3.

Table 4: The outcomes achieved by implementing the proposed algorithms on Dataset 2.

Evaluation Measurements	Results			
Algorithm Name	FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw)	FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw)	FCM(can)-DRLOG(ew)	FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew)
Cumulative Return	1.7741	1.6011	1.6600	1.8738
Annualized Return	214.73%	156.36%	175.54%	251.12%
Annualized Standard Deviation of Returns	0.5189	0.4063	0.5210	0.5721
Annualized Sharpe Ratio	4.0897	3.7867	3.3214	4.3454
Maximum Drawdown	0.2746	0.1173	0.1862	0.2845
Calmar Ratio	7.8192	13.3290	9.4266	8.8257

Figure 3. The daily cumulative return of the proposed algorithms implemented on Dataset 2

Dataset 3- The results obtained from implementing the proposed algorithms on Dataset 3 are shown in Table 5. The FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew) was the best-performing algorithm in terms of returns, with cumulative returns of 1.5482 and an annual percentage yield of 79.66%. In addition, this algorithm not only got the highest returns but also the best risk-adjusted returns with a Calmar ratio of 3.5893. The FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw) algorithm was the lowest-risk option, with an annual standard deviation of 0.4343 and a maximum drawdown of 0.1988. It also achieved the highest annual Sharpe ratio of 1.5693. Figure 4 illustrates the daily cumulative returns resulting from the implementation of the algorithms on Dataset 3.

Table 5: The outcomes achieved by implementing the proposed algorithms on Dataset 3.

Evaluation Measurements	Results			
	FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw)	FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw)	FCM(can)-DRLOG(ew)	FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew)
Cumulative Return	1.3696	1.4899	1.5061	1.5482
Annualized Return	52.43%	70.65%	73.14%	79.66%
Annualized Standard Deviation of Returns	0.4512	0.4343	0.5159	0.5085
Annualized Sharpe Ratio	1.1066	1.5693	1.3692	1.5172
Maximum Drawdown	0.2505	0.1988	0.2693	0.2219
Calmar Ratio	2.0928	3.5535	2.7156	3.5893

Figure 4. The daily cumulative return of the proposed algorithms implemented on Dataset 3

Dataset 4- The evaluation measurements for the proposed algorithms implemented on Dataset 4 are shown in Table 6. According to the results, the FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew) algorithm showed the highest cumulative returns and annual percentage yield of 1.5485 and 79.71%, respectively. This algorithm also recorded the highest Calmar ratio of 9.3147. The FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw) algorithm had the highest annual Sharpe ratio of 3.7930. The FCM(can)-DRLOG(ew) algorithm showed the lowest annual standard deviation of 0.1656 and the smallest maximum drawdown of 0.0603, which makes it the lowest-risk option. Figure 5 presents the daily cumulative returns obtained from implementing the algorithms on Dataset 4.

Table 6: The outcomes achieved by implementing the proposed algorithms on Dataset 4.

Evaluation Measurements	Results			
	FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw)	FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw)	FCM(can)-DRLOG(ew)	FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew)
Cumulative Return	1.4972	1.3779	1.3799	1.5485
Annualized Return	71.77%	53.68%	53.98%	79.71%
Annualized Standard Deviation of Returns	0.1826	0.1834	0.1656	0.2077
Annualized Sharpe Ratio	3.7930	2.7912	3.1078	3.7170
Maximum Drawdown	0.0783	0.0920	0.0603	0.0856
Calmar Ratio	9.1646	5.8321	8.9590	9.3147

Figure 5. The daily cumulative return of the proposed algorithms implemented on Dataset 4

Dataset 5- The evaluation measurements for the proposed algorithms implemented on Dataset 5 are shown in Table 7. Figure 6 shows the daily cumulative returns achieved during the test period. As shown, the FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw) algorithm got the highest cumulative returns and annual percentage yield of 1.7027 and 192.40%, respectively, which makes it the best-performing algorithm in terms of returns. The lowest risk was associated with the FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw) algorithm, which had the lowest annual standard deviation and maximum drawdown of 0.5304 and 0.2434, respectively. The highest annual Sharpe ratio of 3.4301 and the highest Calmar ratio of 7.0460 were achieved by FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw) and FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw) algorithms, respectively. This means that in the Sharpe ratio, higher return lead to a higher risk-adjusted return and in the Calmar ratio, lower risk results in a higher risk-adjusted return.

Table 7: The outcomes achieved by implementing the proposed algorithms on Dataset 5.

Evaluation Measurements	Results			
	FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw)	FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw)	FCM(can)-DRLOG(ew)	FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew)
Cumulative Return	1.7027	1.6412	1.6863	1.5154
Annualized Return	192.40%	171.51%	186.74%	131.17%
Annualized Standard Deviation of Returns	0.5536	0.5304	0.6616	0.5787
Annualized Sharpe Ratio	3.4301	3.1863	2.7848	2.2236
Maximum Drawdown	0.3624	0.2434	0.3669	0.2989
Calmar Ratio	5.3086	7.0460	5.0901	4.3886

Figure 6. The daily cumulative return of the proposed algorithms implemented on Dataset 5

4.3. Results from the implementation of the algorithms on datasets

After analyzing the results of implementing the algorithms on each dataset, it is necessary to compare them with similar algorithms from previous studies. To accomplish this, we compared the evaluation measurements of the proposed algorithms with the BCRP algorithm and the algorithms presented by Abdi et al. (2023) and Khedmati & Azin (2020). These algorithms were selected for comparison because of their similarity and the fact that they have achieved the best results. Comparisons with more basic algorithms are avoided.

Table 8 shows the results of implementing the proposed algorithms in this study and those found in the literature on Dataset 1. According to the results, the FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw) algorithm achieved the highest return and risk-adjusted return on Dataset 1, which outperforms all other algorithms presented in the literature. The annual percentage yield of 192.42% achieved by this algorithm with a 33.98% increase compared to the highest annual percentage yield got from previous algorithms. This shows an improvement of over 20% in return. In fact, most of the proposed algorithms showed significant improvements in both returns and risk-adjusted returns compared to previous algorithms. Previous algorithms exhibited lower risk in terms of both annual standard deviation and maximum drawdown. For a better comparison of the results obtained from implementing the algorithms on Dataset 1, the evaluation metrics of the model are presented in Figure 7.

Table 8: The proposed algorithms in comparison with existing ones in the literature on Dataset 1.

Algorithm Name		S_n	APY	Std	SR	MDD	CR
Proposed Algorithms	FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw)	1.6308	165.94%	0.3241	5.0424	0.1543	10.7552
	FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw)	1.7100	192.42%	0.3556	5.3405	0.1683	11.4331
	FCM(can)-DRLOG(ew)	1.5800	149.65%	0.3569	4.1234	0.1959	7.6391
	FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew)	1.6546	173.76%	0.3571	4.7955	0.1959	8.8697
Benchmark	BCRP	1.4525	110.97%	0.3565	3.0879	0.0899	12.3441
	FCMLOG(euc)	1.5142	129.28%	0.2998	4.2291	0.1213	10.6556
Abdi et al. (2023)	FCMLOG(can)	1.6076	158.44%	0.4041	3.8589	0.1926	8.2279
	FCMLOG(man)	1.4421	107.97%	0.3036	3.4736	0.1297	8.3224
	HRCLOG	1.4509	110.52%	0.2764	3.9666	0.1128	9.7978
Khedmati & Azin (2020)	SPCLOG	1.3053	70.39%	0.3026	2.2971	0.1684	4.1800
	KMDLOG	1.4444	108.64%	0.3238	3.3276	0.1191	9.1218
	KMNLOG	1.317	73.45%	0.2736	2.6521	0.1441	5.0973

Figure 7. The proposed algorithms in comparison with existing ones in the literature on Dataset 1

The results obtained by implementing the proposed algorithms and comparing them to the literature results on Dataset 2 are presented in Table 9. The results show that the highest returns belong to the FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew) algorithm, with an annual percentage yield of 83% higher than the highest

return achieved by previous models. This reflects approximately a 40% improvement in return. However, the high returns obtained from the proposed algorithms are accompanied by higher risk. This means that previous studies have achieved more favorable risk and risk-adjusted return. Figure 8 shows the comparison results from implementing the algorithms on Dataset 2.

Figure 8. The proposed algorithms in comparison with existing ones in the literature on Dataset 2

Table 9: The proposed algorithms in comparison with existing ones in the literature on Dataset 2.

Algorithm Name		S _n	APY	Std	SR	MDD	CR
Proposed Algorithms	FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw)	1.7741	214.73%	0.5189	4.0897	0.2746	7.8192
	FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw)	1.6011	156.36%	0.4063	3.7867	0.1173	13.3290
	FCM(can)-DRLOG(ew)	1.6600	175.54%	0.5210	3.3214	0.1862	9.4266
	FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew)	1.8738	251.12%	0.5721	4.3454	0.2845	8.8257
Benchmark	BCRP	1.8388	238.11%	0.4600	5.1658	0.1386	17.1795
Abdi et al. (2023)	FCMLOG(euc)	1.4401	107.38%	0.3223	3.2537	0.1670	6.4283
	FCMLOG(can)	1.5176	130.32%	0.2763	4.6264	0.0929	14.0208
	FCMLOG(man)	1.6364	167.78%	0.2807	5.8881	0.0727	23.0811
Khedmati & Azin (2020)	HRCLOG	1.2036	44.87%	0.4494	0.9885	0.3574	1.2555
	SPCLOG	1.3332	77.74%	0.4349	1.7769	0.1329	5.8492
	KMDLOG	1.1906	41.74%	0.4442	0.9296	0.1432	2.9149
	KMNLOG	1.4352	105.97%	0.4046	2.6076	0.1517	6.9853

Table 10: The proposed algorithms in comparison with existing ones in the literature on Dataset 3.

Algorithm Name		S_n	APY	Std	SR	MDD	CR
Proposed Algorithms	FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw)	1.3696	52.43%	0.4512	1.1066	0.2505	2.0928
	FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw)	1.4899	70.65%	0.4343	1.5693	0.1988	3.5535
	FCM(can)-DRLOG(ew)	1.5061	73.14%	0.5159	1.3692	0.2693	2.7156
	FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew)	1.5482	79.66%	0.5085	1.5172	0.2219	3.5893
Benchmark	BCRP	1.6360	92.77%	0.5618	1.6481	0.2851	3.2538
	FCMLOG(euc)	1.4083	58.23%	0.4468	1.2475	0.1848	3.1520
Abdi et al. (2023)	FCMLOG(can)	1.2657	37.14%	0.4331	0.7999	0.3446	1.0778
	FCMLOG(man)	1.4243	60.65%	0.4389	1.3250	0.2559	2.3701
	HRCLOG	1.3890	54.98%	0.4888	1.1212	0.3810	1.4431
Khedmati & Azin (2020)	SPCLOG	1.0642	8.65%	0.4163	0.2034	0.4260	0.2029
	KMDLOG	0.9010	-12.98%	0.3879	-0.3393	0.3627	-0.3580
	KMNLOG	1.2642	36.69%	0.4320	0.8452	0.3401	1.0788

Figure 9. The proposed algorithms in comparison with existing ones in the literature on Dataset 3

Table 10 compares the results from implementing the proposed algorithms with those from the literature on Dataset 3. As observed, the algorithms presented in this study have achieved better results in terms of return and risk-adjusted return compared to previous algorithms. The FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew) algorithm achieved nearly a 30% improvement in return compared to the highest return got in previous

models. In addition, the return and risk-adjusted return achieved in this study are considerably closer to those of the benchmark BCRP algorithm. A risk analysis shows that previous algorithms have lower risk, but their returns are considerably lower than those achieved by the proposed algorithms. Figure 9 shows a schematic comparison of the results from implementing the algorithms on Dataset 3.

Figure 10. The proposed algorithms in comparison with existing ones in the literature on Dataset 4

Table 11: The proposed algorithms in comparison with existing ones in the literature on Dataset 4.

Algorithm Name		S_n	APY	Std	SR	MDD	CR
Proposed Algorithms	FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw)	1.4972	71.77%	0.1826	3.7930	0.0783	9.1646
	FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw)	1.3779	53.68%	0.1834	2.7912	0.0920	5.8321
	FCM(can)-DRLOG(ew)	1.3799	53.98%	0.1656	3.1078	0.0603	8.9590
	FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew)	1.5485	79.71%	0.2077	3.7170	0.0856	9.3147
Benchmark	BCRP	1.3080	43.04%	0.2242	1.9132	0.1104	3.8986
	FCMLOG(euc)	1.4209	60.15%	0.2000	2.8820	0.0759	7.9193
Abdi et al. (2023)	FCMLOG(can)	1.4689	67.44%	0.1797	3.6131	0.0457	14.7520
	FCMLOG(man)	1.3724	52.86%	0.2035	2.4750	0.0864	6.1207
	HRCLOG	1.1715	23.50%	0.1605	1.4547	0.0877	2.6798
Khedmati & Azin (2020)	SPCLOG	1.4042	57.24%	0.1679	3.3997	0.0702	8.1541
	KMDLOG	1.2177	30.03%	0.1590	1.8795	0.0991	3.0306
	KMNLOG	1.1002	13.57%	0.1494	0.8986	0.0878	1.5461

Table 11 and Figure 10 display the results obtained by implementing the proposed algorithms and the results from the literature on Dataset 4. The results show that the highest returns achieved by the FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew) algorithm with cumulative returns of 1.5485 and an annual percentage yield of 79.71%. These results show an improvement of over 20% in return compared to previous algorithms. In addition, the FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw) algorithm got the highest Sharpe ratio. The algorithms presented in the literature had a lower risk compared to the algorithms proposed in this study. However, the returns achieved by the proposed algorithms showed a significant improvement and, most times, the risk-adjusted returns have also increased.

Figure 11. The proposed algorithms in comparison with existing ones in the literature on Dataset 5

The results from implementing the proposed algorithms and those from the literature on Dataset 5 are presented in Table 12. The evaluation criteria show that the FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw) algorithm achieved the highest cumulative return of 1.7027. The annual percentage yield of this algorithm is approximately 41% higher than the highest yield obtained by the previous algorithms, which shows an over 30% improvement in returns. The highest Sharpe ratio is associated with this algorithm. The lowest maximum drawdown found in the FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw) algorithm while the lowest annual standard deviation was observed in the previous algorithms. As shown, the proposed algorithms achieved better results in

terms of returns and risk-adjusted returns compared to previous algorithms. Figure 11 shows a comparison of the results from implementing the algorithms on Dataset 5.

Table 12: The proposed algorithms in comparison with existing ones in the literature on Dataset 5.

	Algorithm Name	S_n	APY	Std	SR	MDD	CR
Proposed Algorithms	FCM(can)-DRLOG(uw)	1.7027	192.40%	0.5536	3.4301	0.3624	5.3086
	FCM(man)-DRLOG(uw)	1.6412	171.51%	0.5304	3.1863	0.2434	7.0460
	FCM(can)-DRLOG(ew)	1.6863	186.74%	0.6616	2.7848	0.3669	5.0901
	FCM(man)-DRLOG(ew)	1.5154	131.17%	0.5787	2.2236	0.2989	4.3886
Benchmark	BCRP	1.5270	133.17%	0.7637	1.7417	0.5120	2.6009
Abdi et al. (2023)	FCMLOG(euc)	1.3619	86.40%	0.6304	1.3308	0.3871	2.2318
	FCMLOG(can)	1.5803	151.57%	0.5967	2.4984	0.4460	3.3987
	FCMLOG(man)	1.4947	124.85%	0.5889	2.0776	0.4551	2.7434
Khedmati & Azin (2020)	HRCLOG	1.3326	77.59%	0.4823	1.6057	0.2737	2.8349
	SPCLOG	1.0343	6.97%	0.4394	0.1552	0.3636	0.1917
	KMDLOG	1.2015	44.37%	0.5051	0.8754	0.4301	1.0316
	KMNLOG	1.0170	3.44%	0.4678	0.0703	0.4429	0.0776

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, an online portfolio selection algorithm is presented, which incorporates the pattern-matching principle and fuzzy returns. The optimal portfolio for each day is determined by the algorithm through a meticulous two-step process involving sample selection and portfolio optimization. The first step involves the utilization of two stages of fuzzy clustering to identify similar samples. The initial phase involves clustering fuzzy returns within time windows. If the number of similar data points extracted exceeds a specified threshold, a second phase of fuzzy clustering is conducted on time windows containing trading volumes. In the second step, for portfolio optimization, the logarithmic objective function is used, considering transaction costs and incorporating the dual-beta risk measure. Depending on the market's predicted bullish or bearish trend on the decision day, dual-beta is used. In a bullish market, the goal is to maximize the portfolio's upside beta. Conversely, in a bearish market, the aim is to minimize the downside beta to achieve higher potential returns. In fact, the study aims to maximize returns by utilizing the beta risk measure optimally. Based on the Manhattan and Canberra distance criteria and using simple or weighted linear regression to predict the market trend, four algorithms have been developed in this research. To implement the proposed algorithm, five datasets from the U.S. stock market with diverse characteristics were used. Experimental results show that the proposed approach significantly outperforms several previous algorithms discussed in the literature in terms of both cumulative return and risk-adjusted performance metrics such as Sharpe and Calmar ratios. In particular, the integration of fuzzy clustering and dual-beta effectively enhances the adaptability and responsiveness of the portfolio to varying market conditions. These findings confirm the strength of the model in identifying profitable patterns and controlling risk in dynamic environments. For future research, it is suggested to consider incorporating volatility risk metrics and minimizing them within the model. In addition, considering other indicators in the sample selection process could help to choose the most similar samples and achieve better results.

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